

Magnetic and Spectral Studies on the Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone and its Oxime

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o-Hydroxyacetophenones and their oximes have aroused considerable interest as regards to their chelating ability¹ with the transition metal ions¹⁻³. The present communication deals with the isolation and characterisation of UO_2^{II} complex with HDMA, and Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , VO^{II} , UO_2^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes with HDMAOX.

Experimental

The ligands HDMA and HDMAOX were synthesised as reported earlier³. The micro analysis and estimation of the metal ions were done by the usual methods. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. A Systronic 335 pH-meter was used for the pH measurements. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and the ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of HDMAOX: The metal ion solution was treated with an ethanolic solution of HDMAOX and the mixture digested on a water-bath for ~ 0.5 h. Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Pd^{II} formed buff, green, brown and yellow coloured complexes in the pH range 2.5–9.0, 5.0–9.0, 6.0–9.0 and 1.5–6.5 respectively. The products were filtered, washed with hot water and then with 20% ethanol and finally dried at $105-10^\circ$ in an oven.

Mn^{II} and V^{IV} complexes of HDMAOX: The metal ion solution was treated with an ethanolic solution of HDMAOX and the mixture stirred for ~ 2 h at room temperature. Mn^{II} and V^{IV} formed brownish black and grey coloured complexes in the pH range 8.0–9.0 and 2.5–4.0 respectively. The product was isolated as above.

U^{VI} complexes of HDMA and HDMAOX: A solution of uranyl nitrate was treated with ethanolic solution of HDMA and HDMAOX separately. The

reaction mixtures were stirred for 5–6 h, concentrated under reduced pressure and allowed to stand for ~ 72 h. The yellow crystalline complexes separated out in the pH range 3.0–4.0 and 3.0–4.5 for HDMA and HDMAOX respectively. The products were washed with hot water and then with 20% ethanol and finally dried in vacuum desiccator.

Results and Discussion

The complexes were analysed for C, H, N and the metals (Table 1). The electronic spectra were recorded in solution and the results interpreted in terms of appropriate *d-d* transitions. Some ligand field parameters have also been calculated. The structures of the complexes have been assigned on the basis of their ir spectral data.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra: The Pd^{II} -HDMAOX complex is diamagnetic and exhibits only two bands at 28 570 and 42 850 cm^{-1} . The former is a combination of all the three spin-allowed transitions for a square-planar complex. The values of Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 as obtained from the *d-d* spectra of the complex are 32 070, 1 500 and 500 cm^{-1} respectively. The second band at 42 850 cm^{-1} is due to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transition.

The observed magnetic moment (1.80 B.M.) of the Cu^{II} -HDMAOX complex is very close to the spin-only value for one unpaired electron (1.73 B.M.). Thus the orbital contribution is almost quenched by the crystalline field. The electronic spectra of the complex show three bands at 16 050, 20 000 and 22 600 cm^{-1} due to the transitions $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$, $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ and charge transfer respectively, suggesting a square-planar arrangement⁴.

The observed magnetic moment of the Ni^{II} -HDMAOX complex suggests it to be diamagnetic and square-planar. Three well-defined bands at 17 060, 19 000 and 29 700 cm^{-1} are observed corresponding to the transitions $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ respectively. The values of Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 are found to be 20 560, 10 440 and 4 200 cm^{-1} respectively.

The observed magnetic moment (4.32 B.M.) of the Co^{II} -HDMAOX complex suggests it to be tetrahedral⁵. The two bands at 7 320 and 11 780 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complex may be assigned to $^4A_2(F) \rightarrow ^4T_1(F) [\nu_2]$ and $^4A_2(F) \rightarrow ^4T_1(P) [\nu_3]$ transitions respectively. The values of B' , β and λ were calculated using the equations suggested by Figgis⁴. The values of β is comparable to that reported for a tetrahedral complex.

The observed magnetic moment (1.71 B.M.) of the VO^{II} -HDMAOX complex is quite close to the spin-only value for one unpaired electron (1.73 B.M.). Hence orbital contribution is completely quenched. The electronic spectra of the complex show three bands at 13 600, 18 200 and 26 000 cm^{-1} . The first is assigned to an unresolved band resulting from $^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E_1$ transition, the second to the transition $^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_1$ and the third may either be assigned to

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
			C	H	N	Metal
C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂	White	142	66.96 (67.04)	7.12 (7.26)	7.12 (7.82)	—
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Buff	278	57.50 (57.28)	5.60 (5.72)	6.70 (6.67)	15.25 (15.13)
Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Green	~300	57.90 (57.87)	5.75 (5.78)	6.70 (6.75)	14.20 (14.15)
Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Brown	230	57.50 (57.84)	5.60 (5.78)	6.50 (6.74)	14.10 (14.19)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Brownish black	250	58.25 (58.39)	5.75 (5.83)	6.75 (6.81)	13.30 (13.38)
Pd(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Yellow	286	51.90 (51.98)	5.19 (5.30)	6.05 (6.12)	23.00 (23.50)
VO(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Grey	178d	56.70 (56.73)	5.65 (5.67)	6.60 (6.61)	12.20 (12.05)
UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Orange	205	38.30 (38.33)	3.75 (3.83)	4.40 (4.47)	38.00 (38.02)
C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	Brown	55	73.25 (73.17)	7.25 (7.31)	—	—
UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂) ₂	Orange	195	40.06 (40.26)	3.50 (3.69)	—	40.00 (39.94)

${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transition or to the low energy charge transfer and inter-ligand transition. This complex appears to be five-coordinate with O of the vanadyl group lying at the apex of a square based pyramid, N and O of the ligand forming the basal plane.

The observed magnetic moment (5.86 B.M.) of the Mn^{II}-HDMAOX indicates five unpaired electrons. The d^5 -configuration being spherically symmetrical, the ground state suffers no change in the stereochemistry. Both the octahedral and the tetrahedral d^5 ions have the same order of energy levels. The 17 200, 18 750, 20 000, 21 200, 22 450 and 27 500 cm^{-1} bands in the complex correspond to the transitions ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(G)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(D)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$ and ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$ respectively. The tetrahedral nature of the complex has been confirmed on the basis of its molar absorbance value⁶.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of the ligands show strong bands at 3 380 (OH chelated), 3 240 (OH for N-OH), 2 920, 2 850 (CH of methylene groups) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (C-N).

The ir spectra of the chelates show that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal as the band at 3 380 cm^{-1} (OH chelated) disappears in the complexes. The strong band at 1 640 cm^{-1} (C-N) shifts from 20–10 cm^{-1} to lower frequency in the metal chelates indicating that N of the =N-OH group coordinates with the metal ion in case of HDMAOX. The $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ band at 980 cm^{-1} in the ligand HDMAOX shifts to 974–960 cm^{-1} in the chelates, a position recommended by various workers^{7,8}. The bands at 990 and 935 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-U=O}}$ respectively⁹. The bands at 515–550 and 550–590 cm^{-1} indicate M-O and M-N bands respectively¹⁰, which may also be coupled with the ligand bands.

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Spectrophotometric Study on some Palladium(II) Hydrazopyrazolone Complexes

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METAL complexes of azopyrazolone compounds are of great importance in technical dye chemistry^{1,2}. They are more resistant to chemical reagents than the metal-free dyes. Complex formation has a favourable effect on the stability of the azo bridge³. Also, colour of the azo compounds is greatly